

IMPACT OF FOOD WASTE ON FOOD INSECURITY (THE ROLE OF CONSUMER ATTITUDES IN HOUSEHOLDS AS A MODERATING FACTOR)

By

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Abstract

Food insecurity in Togo is a threatening phenomenon. Having observed that a lot of food is thrown away by households, it was important to see whether this waste had any impact on food insecurity. The other point was to see whether the household's attitude affected the relationship between these two variables. That is, to see if household attitude played a moderating role between food waste and food insecurity. A survey was therefore carried out on a sample of 272 people, using a questionnaire. We adopted quantitative method. The results of our empirical study indicate that food waste has an impact on food insecurity in our context (Togo), and that household attitudes also play a moderating role in this relationship. Inherent implications for researchers and practitioners alike were also suggested. It would therefore be worthwhile for the Togolese government and all relevant institutions to conduct an awareness-raising campaign within households to reduce this phenomenon.

Key Words: *Consumer attitude, food insecurity, Food waste, house hold*

1. Justification of the Study

Global food insecurity is increasing by the day, plunging people into unprecedented famine. According to the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization's report on the state of food security and nutrition in the world, published in 2022, more than 828 million people were suffering from hunger in 2021", 103 million more between 2019 and 2020 and 46 million more in 2021, if we take into account the middle of the range. According to the report's projections, nearly 670 million people will still be suffering from hunger in 2030. While the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimates that around a third of food produced for human consumption is lost worldwide (FAO 2011 2013). Food is lost or wasted throughout the supply chain, from primary agricultural production to final consumption in households. In Togo, more than 386,069 people suffered from acute food insecurity over the period from June to August 2022, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations in Togo (FAO-Togo) information note published on July 07, 2022. In Togo, food waste represents 40% of agricultural production. For the Minister of the Environment and Forest Resources, Dédé Ahoéfa Ekoué, this situation is unacceptable. She declared: "This waste is unacceptable at a time when millions of people are suffering from hunger. With a growing impact on our environment, we need to find more sustainable methods of food production. We need to think about what we eat in order to save our planet". In this context, we ask ourselves what impact food waste have on food insecurity, and attempt to see if there is any moderating effect of household attitudes on the relationship between food waste and food insecurity in Togo.

The aim of this study is to analyze the influence of food waste on food insecurity and to see if there is any moderating effect on household attitudes linked to the relationship between these two concepts in order to shed light on the causes of food insecurity in Togo and tried to propose solutions to combat it.

2. Theoretical Framework of the Research

2.1 SECTION 1: Food Waste

2.1.1 Definition of loss and waste

The definition of the word "waste" is not the same for all consumers. Similarly, in the scientific and political environment, the contours of what constitutes food waste are neither unique nor universally accepted. Some define food waste as "food intended for human consumption that is lost, discarded or wasted at some point in the food chain (Gustafsson and Lundqvist 2012). According to this definition, food "intended for human consumption" that is diverted to animal feed or compost constitutes waste in the same way as food discarded in the household garbage. Food degradation (for example, the loss of vitamins from cut fruit left to oxidize in

the open air) is also waste under this definition. Other definitions distinguish between different uses (or non-uses) of products that are not consumed by humans but were originally intended for them (e.g. FUSIONS (Drivers of Current Food Waste Generation, Threats of Future Increase and Opportunities for Reduction, (Gao et al. 2021). Additional difficulties arise from the use of the word "loss" for some actors (farms, agribusiness) and the word "waste" for others (consumers). The term "waste" has a more negative connotation than "loss", and in particular implies a certain responsibility/blame on the part of the one who causes the waste (whereas the one who suffers the loss is the victim). This can lead to feelings of guilt and/or excessive blame among some consumers. The word "waste" itself is problematic: while it may refer to an objective and (not always) clearly defined concept, it tends to mingle quickly and naturally with value judgments either latent in the mind of the researcher, who as a citizen/consumer is inevitably involved in the or manifest in the minds of some interviewees.

The problem of waste can only be tackled in a relevant way if objectives and definitions are clearly formulated and compatible with each other. In our work because it is necessary to give a definition of the word waste, we will retain the FAO definition mentioned at the beginning: Any food intended for human consumption that is lost, discarded or adulterated at any stage of the food chain is food waste (FAO 2011 2013)

3. SECTION 2: Food Safety and Insecurity

3.1 Definition of Food Security and Food Insecurity

Food security refers to "the ability of an individual to obtain food in quantity and quality at the lowest cost, at any time and in any place, in order to lead a healthy and active life" (Mechlem 2004). The term is multi-dimensional, multi-sectoral and multi-disciplinary, and rests on four fundamental pillars: (i) the availability of basic foodstuffs in sufficient quantity and quality; (ii) the accessibility of basic foodstuffs, in all places and at all times, for everyone, including the most vulnerable groups; (iii) healthy use (sanitary quality of food and nutritional balance) ; and (iv) stability of supply.

To achieve food security : (i) food is available not just for one category of people, but for the whole population, including the most vulnerable; (ii) food is accessible to the population economically, in time and space; (iii) food meets health, safety and hygiene standards, and that the diet is balanced in terms of protein, energy and micronutrient intake; and (iv) supplies cover the whole year, not just part of it, and the mechanisms in place enable us to deal with crises and emergencies. Food insecurity occurs when the availability of safe, nutritious food and the ability to obtain satisfactory food by socially acceptable means are limited or uncertain (Radimer et al. 1992) ; (Anderson 1990 cited in (A. Hamelin, Bolduc, and Amelin 2019)). There are different methods for measuring food insecurity, and much of the work aimed at developing measurement tools is based

on the research of Radimer et al. And Wehler, Scott and Anderson (Melchior et al. 2012). Food insecurity is often measured by concerns about food shortages, lack of food variety or even food shortages due to lack of money (A. M. Hamelin, Beaudry, and Habicht 2002).

4. SECTION 3: Consumer Attitudes

4.1 Concepts of Consumer Attitudes

Eating habits" refer to what and how we eat, including how we prepare, buy and handle food, as well as how we perceive, appreciate and care for food. Eating habits are constantly evolving. They adapt to major societal changes that lead to modifications in lifestyle and consumption values (Beciu, Arghiroiu, and Bobeică 2024). Until the 1940s, food self-sufficiency was a fundamental principle for families. Paradoxically, however, as incomes rose, food budgets fell while spending increased, catering and ready-made meals became more widespread, and globalization led to a diversification of foods, meals and practices (Francis 2015). All these factors have fundamentally changed the characteristics of consumers, who have diversified and, above all, are looking for a certain type of sophisticated, pleasurable food at a lower price (Le Borgne, Sirieix, and Costa 2015). Today, environmental and nutritional standards increasingly influence consumer behavior and food choices (Pinto 2022). These changes in eating habits not only affect the demand for food, but also the value consumers place on it.

5. Conceptual Framework: Food Waste and Food Insecurity

The first Millennium Development Goal of the United Nations (UN) was to halve the number of hungry people by 2015 (United Nations, n.d.). Progress has been made, but the target has not yet been reached. Yet food production is sufficient to meet people's current needs. Today, more than 805 million people do not have enough to eat every day, or one in nine individuals (McGuire 2015). According to the FAO, 1.3 billion tons of food are thrown away every year (Evans and Nagele 2018). The food wasted globally would be enough to feed hungry populations (Stuart, 2013). In Togo, more than 386,069 people suffered from acute food insecurity over the period from June to August 2022, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations briefing note in Togo (FAO-Togo, Partners, 2020) published on July 07, 2022; while food waste represents 40% of agricultural production. This leads us to our hypothesis that food waste influences food insecurity.

- **H₁**: Food waste has an impact on food insecurity.

5.1 Household attitudes to the relationship between food waste and food insecurity

In this paper, we examine food waste at restaurant level in private households. The following diagram summarizes the possible origins and destinations of food that passes through the household and is then neither consumed by the household nor passed on to others.

Figure 1 : Origins And Possible Destinations Of Wasted Food

Source : WRAP, 2009

An estimated 931 million tonnes of food, or 17% of the total food available to consumers in 2019, was thrown away in household, retail, restaurant and other food service garbage cans, according to a new UN study conducted to support global efforts to halve food waste by 2030. The report finds that in almost every country that measured food waste, it was significant, regardless of income level. Most of this waste comes from households, which reject 11% of the total food available at the consumption stage in the supply chain, says the report. Food services and retail outlets waste 5% and 2% respectively. Globally, 121 kilograms of food are wasted each year at the consumer level, 74 kilograms of which occur in households. Based on the above, we can therefore advance our second hypothesis that consumer attitudes at household level play a moderating role in the relationship between food waste and food insecurity.

- **H2:** Household consumer attitudes play a moderating role in the relationship between food waste and food insecurity.

Figure 2: Research conceptual model

Research conceptual model

Methods

Introduction

The choice of a research method depends on the purpose of the study, whether it is to explore phenomena, describe the characteristics of a population, examine association relationships between variables or predict causal relationships (Fortin 2010). This research utilized in carrying out and carefully examinations of the data sources and techniques used for data analysis. It also focuses on which information is collected, analyzed, and interpreted. The methodology contains the research design, population and sample size, sampling techniques, data Collection, and analysis

6.1 Research Design

Two main methodological approaches often adopted to conduct scientific research: qualitative and quantitative (Muijs et al. 2004). The primary objective of this study was to investigate the influences of consumer attitude that revenges the insecurity in the developing country called Togo. To attain this objective, the study adopted both descriptive and explanatory research design. Methods used to calculate, describe, and summarize collected research data in a logical, meaningful, and efficient way refer to specific descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics are reported numerically in the manuscript text and/or in its tables, or graphically in its figures (Vetter 2017). The descriptive research design was used for describing the existing situation or phenomenon of the study in detail besides the examination of the cause-and-effect relationship between food

waste and food insecurity by having consumer attitude as moderating variables. Research design reported about forty mixed methods in the literature (Tashakkori and Teddlie 2003). (Clark, Gutmann, and Hanson 2007) identified the six most often used design, which include three concurrent and three sequential design. One of those designs, the mixed-methods sequential explanatory design, is highly popular among researchers and implies collecting and analyzing first quantitative and then qualitative data in two consecutive phases within one study. Therefore, this current research employed an explanatory research design to explain the influences of independent variables upon the dependent variable.

6.2. Research Approach

Our research problem is of an explanatory or even causal nature; so, depending on the requirements linked to the information we need to gather, a quantitative methodology is the best solution. Our research therefore based on a hypothetical-deductive approach, which consists in "following a linear and invariant process aimed at translating theoretical analyses into research hypotheses, which are then tested in the field through empirical situations considered to be representative".

To gain the advantage of the quantitative research method, this research adopted only the meta-quantitative data approach. Even though there are arguments on incompatible scientific paradigms of the strategies, the advocates (McCann 2022) of this method, usage argued pragmatism research philosophy is always out of the dilemma. A quantitative approach adopted to generalize the findings resulting from descriptive and inferential statistics. We carried out an empirical study based on a questionnaire survey and tested it in the context of our research. To facilitate the suitability and validation of the 5-point measurement scales, a pre-test carried out.

6.3. Target population

Anyone who has been living in Togo Lome City participated in this research as the best respondent because food waste is everywhere in personal homes, cafeterias, hotels, and business industries due to spoilage, expiration, excesses, and others, as reported by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2022.

6.4. Sampling Technique

A sample described as subset of population or selected representative of larger population. (Kombo and Tromp (2009) defined the population sample as a set of respondents selected from a larger population for a survey. To investigate the influence of consumer attitude on the food insecurity paradigm, a sample size selected to meet the objective of the study, non-probability, by using the judgmental sampling technique employed. In the sample, the researchers shared it with members in the lomé city and got 272 submissions within two months, which describes the event well.

The aim of this pre-test is to ensure that respondents have a good grasp of the subject, to detect and correct as far as possible any errors that may nevertheless hinder comprehension of the questions asked, and to see whether the latter are in line with the technical terms used. This pre-test revealed that the questions as formulated were comprehensible to the respondents. This enabled us to proceed with the actual data collection. Next, final survey carried out on a sample of mentioned peoples, most of them households. This enabled us to verify the proposed research hypotheses.

6.5. Data sources

Both primary and secondary data collected for the study to achieve the desired objectives. Primary data collected through administered questionnaires, and secondary data collected through document surveys with FAO, WHO, countryside NGOs, and the Togo Security Minister in 2023.

6.6 Data Collection

Given the characteristics of our target population, the collection of our quantitative data took place in household departments and households' homes. The data collection period ran from **February 20 to April 24, 2024**. Given that we had to interview individuals one by one, it took us quite a long time to collect the data.

6.7. Data Analysis

Before the actual data analysis, the data obtained through questionnaires validated. The returned instrument scrutinized to determine its correctness and accuracy. Data analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of the Kobo toolbox, Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25, and AMOS 25 with the help of SPD 23. Having these, specifically the we tested by using Bartheltt splicity tests for its significancy, factorized for data consitancy and measuring the something in it, data fairness by using eigenvalue, KMO for the value that 50% above or not.

Besides these, univariate and linear regression analysis were applied.

6.7. 1 Model Specification

This study utilized regression model to establish the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The model takes the following equation:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * X + \epsilon$$

Where :

- Y : food insecurity
- β_0 : is the intercept and
- β_1 : is the slope.
- X : food waste
- ϵ : error level or percistion (5%)

- Consumer attitude is a moderating variable that influences the relationship between food waste and food insecurity.

8. DATA ANALYSIS

8.1. Data Analysis Methods

To process and analyze the quantitative data collected, we used factor analysis, univariate analysis and linear regression analysis. In this case, SPSS 25 software was used to enter, process and analyze the data collected.

8.1.1. Principal component analysis (PCA) and scale reliability testing

Factor analysis enabled us to test the internal consistency of each scale using principal component analysis (PCA), followed by calculation of Cronbach's alpha and Joreskog's Rhô. This enables latent factors to be extracted from the initial observable variables, so as to restore the maximum amount of information (variance explained). However, before proceeding with a factor analysis, it is necessary to check whether the data are metric and factorizable.

The Kaiser, Meyer and Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett's sphericity test can be used to check the factorability of the data.

8.1.2 PCA and reliability test for the "food insecurity" variable

The table below shows that the KMO index has a value of 0.695 greater than 0.5. We can deduce that the selected items share enough variance with the factor or axis to which they are linked. Bartlett's sphericity test gives sig. = 0.000: the data are sufficiently correlated and can therefore be factorized. In view of the above, the factorial model thus produced is adequate and relevant for data analysis. The contribution of each item exceeds 0.5. Thus, these selected items are represented and coherent, proving that they contribute to measuring the same thing. The visualization of the table shows that the total variance explained by single component (factor or axis) is 67.586. Moreover, the eigenvalue of this factor is 2.177, which is well above 1. This is a fairly satisfactory value, in line with the required standards for the choice of factors or axes that provide more information for data analysis.

Table 1 : KMO and Food Insecurity Reliability Test

Item loadings of the adapted Radimer/Cornell questionnaire

8.1.3 Principal Component Analysis and Reliability Test for Consumer Attitude Variable

Items	Intitulés des items de FI	Extraction	Composante
FI1	I wonder if the food I can afford to buy for my household will be enough	0.570	0.671
FI2	I'd used up all the food I'd bought and had no money to buy more.	0.742	0.641
FI3	We eat the same thing several days in a row because we only have a few items on hand and no money to buy more.	0.667	0.727
FI4	I'm often hungry, but I don't eat because I can't afford enough food.	0.725	0.714
Cronbach Alpha		0.631	
Eigenvalue		2.177	
Explanatory variance in percent		67.586	
Sampling decision (KMO)		0.695	
Barthlett sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	121.436	
	Degree of freedom	6	
	Test significance	0.000	

Source : SPSS25, 2024 Survey data

The **table 2** below shows that the KMO index has a value of 0.776 greater than 0.5. We can deduce that the items selected share enough variance with the factor or axis to which they are linked. Barthlett's sphericity test gives sig: = 0.000: the data are sufficiently correlated and can therefore be factorised. In view of the above, the factorial model thus produced is adequate and relevant for analysing the data. The contribution of each item exceeds 0.5. The items selected are therefore represented and consistent, proving that they contribute to measuring the same thing. The table shows that the total variance explained by single component (factor or axis) is 65.646. Furthermore, the eigenvalue of this factor is 2.12, which is well above 1. A fairly satisfactory value.

Table 2: KMO and Household Attitude Reliability Test

Item loadings of the adapted Radimer/Cornell questionnaire

Items	Attitude item titles	Extraction	Composante
CA1	Throwing food away is something I often do	0.667	0.676
CA2	Throwing away food is something I do automatically	0.594	0.720
CA3	Throwing food away is something I do without paying attention to it	0.562	0.736
CA4	Throwing away food is part of my daily routine	0.634	0.749
CA5	Throwing away food is something I've been doing for a long time	0.826	0.596
Cronbach Alpha		0.733	
Eigenvalue		2.12	
Explanatory variance in percent		65.646	
Sampling decision (KMO)		0.776	
Barthlett sphericity test	Chi-square approximation	257.882	
	Degree of freedom	10	
	Test significance	0.000	

Source : SPSS25, 2024 Survey data

8.1.4 PCA and reliability test for the "Food wastage" variable

The **table 3 below** shows that the KMO index has a value of 0.611 which is greater than 0.5. We can deduce that the items selected share enough variance with the factor or axis to which they are linked. Barthlett's sphericity test gives sig: = 0.000: the data are sufficiently correlated and can therefore be factorised. In view of the above, the factorial model thus produced is adequate and relevant for analysing the data. The contribution of each item exceeds 0.5. The items selected are therefore represented and consistent, proving that they contribute to measuring the same thing. The table shows that the total variance explained by single component (factor or axis) is 67.601. Furthermore, the eigenvalue of this factor is 2.18, which is well above 1. A fairly satisfactory value.

Table 3: KMO And Reliability Test For Food Waste

Item loadings of the adapted Radimer/Cornell questionnaire

Items	Item titles Food waste	Extraction	Composante
WF1	The other members of my household don't like it when I try to use older foods.	0.752	0.530
WF2	Food is natural and decomposes in landfill sites, so I don't mind throwing it away.	0.689	0.609
WF3	I want to eat only the freshest foods, so throwing out the less fresh foods doesn't bother me too much	0.660	0.758
WF4	Uneaten food from my household is composted, so I don't mind throwing it away.	0.603	0.724
Cronbach Alpha			0.563
Eigenvalue			2.18
Explanatory variance in percent			67.601
Sampling decision (KMO)			0.611
Barthlett sphericity test		Chi-square approximation	101.562
		Degree of freedom	6
		Test significance	0.000

Figure 3 : AMOS Modele Formulation Diagram

Figure 3 shows the structural model of the influence of food waste on food insecurity. Through the model, we can easily see the contribution of each item. This model comes from AMOS 25 software.

Figure 4 : Moderation Diagram

Figure 4 shows the structural model of moderation between the independent variable (food waste) and the dependent variable (food insecurity).

Source Amos 25

Table 4: Indicators And Parameters for The Analysis of Covariance

GFI : and AGFI

Indexe	Descriptions	Key values
Absolute Indexes	It measures the relative share explained by the variance, covariance of the model. GFI and AGFI "evaluate the quality of a model in absolute terms, but do not allow us to assess the value at which a model can be considered valid" (Valette-Florence, 1993). Sensitive to model complexity	> 0.9 (Didellon & Valette-Florence, 1996). The complexity of the model may penalise the quality of this adjustment.
GFI		
AGFI	It measures the relative proportion of the variance Covariance explained by the model adjusted by the number of variables in relation to the number of degrees of freedom. Sensitive to model complexity	> 0.8 (Pedhazur & Schmelkin) the complexity of the model risks penalising the quality of this adjustment
Chi-square	It measures the lack of fit resulting from the restrictions of the model (fixed parameters). Sensitive to sample size	No key value exists
Chi-square/ Number of df	It measures how well the factor structure model fits the empirical data. Sensitive to sample size	< 5 or if possible < 2 (Pedhazur & Schmelkin)
RMR	Standardised version of the RMR, representing the average appreciation of residuals	Closest to zero, acceptable up to 0.1 (Roussel, Durrieu, Campy, & El Akremi, 2002)
RMSEA	Average difference per degree of freedom expected in the total population and in the sample. Independent of sample size and model complexity	< 0.08 and if possible < 0.05
Indices Incremental	It compares the lack of fit of the model to be tested with that of the base model. Not recommended for models < 150	0.9
TLI		
CFI	Measures the relative reduction in the lack of fit (sensitive to the estimation method)	0.9
Indices Sparsimony	These information-theoretic indices penalise complex models	BIC < BIC saturated.
BIC		

Source : (Roussel, Durrieu, Campy, & El Akremi, 2002) cité par (Meziou, 2010)

8.1.5 Results of CFA: CFA of the Global Measurement Model

With six (06) items at the outset, the food waste scale after cleaning gives us five (04) items, those of food insecurity four (04) out of six (06) and those of attitude five (05) out of six (06). These items make up the set of manifest variables on which the CFA was carried out using AMOS 23 software.

Table 5 : Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Index	Values recorded
Chi-square	34.28
Degree of freedom	19
P	0.002
Chi-square/degrees of freedom	1.8
GFI	0.969
AGFI	0.942
RMR	0.102
RMSEA	0.054
TLI	0.903
CFI	0.934
Model BIC/ Saturated BIC	276.086/304.386

Source: AMOS25, 2024 survey data

8.1.6 Presentation and Analysis of Results of Hypothesis Testing

Table 6: Estimation Of Model Parameters

Relationship between variables		R	S.E.	T	P
WF	→	0.507	0.167	3.041	0.002

Source : AMOS25, 2024 survey data

8.1.6. 1 Test of the Influence of Food Waste on Food Insecurity

Looking at the results in the table 6 above, the correlation coefficient between waste food and food insecurity is positive (0.507). The probability p is less than 5%, and the student's t-test is greater than 1.96 (3.041). These results therefore confirm that food waste influences food insecurity, thereby validating hypothesis H1.

8.1.6.2 Hypothesis testing of the Moderating Effect of Consumer attitude On the Relationship between Food Waste and Food Insecurity

Table 7: Result of the moderating effect of Consumer attitude on the relationship between waste food and food insecurity

Variables	Coefficient	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	498.2183	8.1299	0.0000	377.5626	68.8741
WF	0.0211	0.2538	0.7998	-0.1424	0.1846
CA	0.0402	2.2177	0.2741	0.0045	0.0758
Interaction between WF and CA	0.0001	0.8779	0.3808	0.0000	0.0000

Source : Hayes process 2024

According to the results in the table 7 above, the interaction effect is zero (0) ($d = 0.000$; t is positive; $p = 0.3808 > 0.05$). Thus, these values allow us to assert that household attitude has an influence on the relationship of food waste to food insecurity in Togo Lome in our research context.

Furthermore, the confidence interval ($LLCI = 0.000$ and $ULCI = 0.000$) is zero.

In view of the above results, we can affirm that household attitude plays a moderating role between food waste and food insecurity in Togo. Thus, hypothesis H_2 is validated in our research.

9. Discussion

In this study, we asked ourselves whether food waste could have an impact on food insecurity in Togo Lome, and also whether household attitudes played a moderating role in the relationship between food waste and food insecurity. The results of our study confirmed hypothesis 1, which clearly attests to the fact that food waste has an impact on food insecurity; this, moreover, is in line with the Minister's statement that food waste accounts for 40% of agricultural production, while people are dying of hunger. The results also show that household or consumer attitudes play a moderating role in this relationship: the more food you waste, the more you contribute to food insecurity. In other words, it confirms our second hypothesis that household or consumer attitude plays a moderating role in the relationship between food waste and food insecurity.

10. Conclusion

The present study investigated the impact of food waste on food insecurity and the moderating role that household or consumer attitudes to food waste could play in food insecurity. To verify this, a questionnaire administered to 272 households, and the responses obtained at the end of the survey confirmed a considerable impact of food waste on food insecurity in Togo. The results also confirmed that household attitudes play a moderating role in this relationship. The results of our study present both interesting managerial and theoretical contributions. Indeed, from theoretical point of view, no research to our knowledge has looked into the impact that food waste could have on food insecurity in Togo Lome, and the role that households could play in this relationship. What's more, these results are of interest not only to the researcher, but also to the practitioner. Indeed, from a practical point of view, these results may also be of interest to the Togolese state in conducting an awareness-raising session within households in Togo to limit food waste in order to contribute to food security. It is important to emphasize that, despite its considerable theoretical and practical contributions, this study is not without its weaknesses. Indeed, our study was limited to the household level, whereas study could have looked at food waste at the level of the production and distribution chain. Besides these, the sample size represents shortcoming and larger sample size that probably have enabled greater generalization. On the other hand, it is possible to envisage a number of future research avenues. We could try to see whether the relationship between food waste and food insecurity is linked to societal attitude variables. Moreover, we tried to convince and checked whether consumer attitude play a moderating role in this relationship. It is also possible to see the impact that awareness-raising can have on food waste.

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